

Peter Mac
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Our journey incorporating AI into our cancer computational research

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Computational Biology Program
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About me

Venezuela

**Universidad
Simon Bolivar**

Bachelor of Biology
Honours year in cellular
neuroscience

2005-2011

2013-2014

MSc
Bio-
informatics

2015-2018

PhD Cancer
Bioinformatics

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Bulk RNAseq
SNPs/copy number
Network analysis

2019 - 2020

Spatial
proteomics data

Started
collaborating
with clinicians

2021-2023

Single-cell
RNAseq,
multiome
DNAseq

2024

Spatial
transcriptomics

2025

The Trigos Lab

Computational Biology Program

We focus on understanding treatment resistance and response from a cancer evolution and ecosystems perspective

- Omics data (genomics, transcriptomics, epigenomics, single-cell, etc) and patient imaging
- Bioinformatics, computational biology, engineering, maths/stats, deep learning
- Have our own biological research questions and also develop bioinformatics methods

Primarily multiple myeloma and prostate cancer, but we also apply our methods to other cancers

‘Limitations of bioinformatics (-omics)’

- Largely, tissue-based
- Captures only a part of the story (‘phenotype’) of the disease
- In a single location, at a single time point in time (representative?)
- How to translate findings to patients?
 - Treatments? (extensive wet-lab validation)
 - Biomarkers?

AI vs AI vs AI

AI to make your
life easier

AI as new
algorithms

AI that expands the
types of data I can
look at beyond what I
can do with
traditional
bioinformatics

What we want to do

Multi-omics

Better understand disease
'phenotype'

Better predict patient response

Shagera et al. Journal of Nuclear Medicine. 2022, 63 (8) 1191-1198; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2967/jnumed.121.263006>

From bioinformatics to AI

Collaborations & funding

- Large cohort studies
- Standard-of-care samples (caveats)

Collaborations

- What problem are you trying to solve?
- Survival? Progression? Pathology classification?

Funding – opens other funding opportunities

Patients

- Patient – consent for data to be used for research
- Ethics applications
- Governance applications

- Bias in AI: ethnicity and race
 - What to do about it?
 - Does the data exist?
 - If not, how to get it?
 - If yes, is it reliable?

Other biases?

The more data, the noisier the data

Data

- Logistics for data generation (paperwork!) (pathologist!) (core facility!)
- Logistics to find and de-identify data
 - Patient medical records
 - Nurses
 - Clinical trial coordinators
 - Medical physicists
 - Anatomical pathologists

Staff and students

- Bioinformaticians learning “AI on the job”
- Computer scientist

Linkages with
University Comp
Sci departments

Compute

- HPC systems for “genomics” might not work for “AI”

pawsey

NCI
AUSTRALIA

- Can we transfer the data?
- Who do we need to ask for permission?
- Who *owns* the data?
- Policy?
- Governance?

NCMAS

More advanced HPC
skills needed

We publish!!!
Yey!!!!!!

How do we then
translate it to the
clinic???????

Translation

- An AI tool is a 'product', not a drug
- Falls under category of a 'medical test'
- Your 'product' uses a model trained on patient data
- New territory in Australia

- Any considerations on how we shape our research to prepare for this?

Conclusions

- Extending research to include AI -> not just about learning new methods, need to build ecosystem
- Collaborations more with clinicians rather than biologists

Lab members

James Comben
 Xiang Guo
 Sirui Weng
 David Le
 Lachlan Cain
 Yeung-Ae Park
 Mevan Ekanayke
 Sasuni Hirimuthugoda

Clinical Collaborators

Amit Khot
 Michael Hofman
 Arun Azad
 Chris Yates (RMH)
 James King (RMH)
 Shahneen Sandhu

